

Research article

Factors Affecting the Job fulfillment of Employees; A case study of Cement factories industry in Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract: The purpose of this investigative study is to decide the most persuasive components influencing the activity fulfillment and general occupation fulfillment (GOF) of workers. The study carried out at Cement industry in Sindh, Pakistan. The rewarded workers are essential driver for achievement of the association. Significance and need of fulfilled representatives are inescapable, and their assistance is to build the benefit and hold the association notoriety in each focused market (FM). The information has been gathered through different sources including essential and auxiliary sources, 327 questionnaires were conveyed among the workers of different Cement factories in the distinctive areas of the province. This examination has been led with the graphic and inferential measurements, Pareto investigation and connection coefficient to decide the most powerful factors influencing the activity fulfillment of workers and to break down the connections between the general occupation fulfillment, characteristic, and outward factors which impact the general occupation fulfillment of representatives in Cement factories of Sindh. Open finished inquiries in Likert scale arranged and sorted out to gather the information. The outcomes are very shocking so that the representatives denied the frame sensible pay benefits in solid working conditions, which justify based incidental advantages, accomplishments and gaining from work-itself. Different proposals of this examine exploration are featured and prescribed to the government and to the partners. The constraints and strategy for future heading of research are likewise talked about.

Keywords: HC (Human Capital), Job fulfillment (JF), ES (Employee Satisfaction), GOF (general occupation fulfillment), FM (Focused Market).

1. Introduction

Organizations have started to move globally to get the general marketing benefits since the latest two decades and admitting, without focusing on HR Policies like making capacities among employees, engaging work, ethics and working conditions can't sustain in the forceful market

(FM), since all advantages can be imitated yet specific capacity, ability, learning and experience of human capital (HC) can't reproduced. Therefore, it is very difficult to keep staff satisfied with the long-term organization. As employees willing to work as the backbone of organizational success, they are also more susceptible for creative testing; reaching breakthroughs that enable the company to take care of them, change the time, and different market conditions. In addition, researchers identified the perspective of employee satisfaction with work that enhanced when the work is more attractive or diverse (Dinler, 2008). Disturbing the level of job satisfaction for employees who are the benefited of salaries, working conditions, promotions, extra benefits, achievements and work facilities. Around the world, people work to get a healthy salary to live a better life. The staffs are not very happy with the organizations which have a serious impact on the appearance of a particular product. In today's preparation, where there is no shortage of competitors in the market it is necessary for the organization to retain satisfied with employees as their work can be done with dedication and honesty. No one needs to leave his service every six months, but when there is no supportive role for the organization; people turn to be better in opportunities. As for Saeed (2013) stressed that dissatisfaction creates when the organization does not influence the factors that affect employee satisfaction as defined by Nasir (2012), opportunities, stress, leadership, labor standards, power, employment, salary, promotion of supervisors working groups, and working conditions that affect employee job fulfillment (JF). Employees are analyzed by their outlook about positive or negative function. The positively behavior indicates satisfaction and the negativity shows dissatisfaction. According to Herzberg (1966), two factors are fundamental theory ("recognition, independence, achievement, etc."), "work environment, salaries and enormous benefits", etc. The intrinsic factors are called catalysts and external factors called hygiene; while externalism creates dissatisfaction, while intrinsic factors create motivation among employees. Most of the organizations are working on external factors that affect more than the core factors on job fulfillment (JF) staff. In the mature world, this function is an unavoidable share that can be spent from life. Job fulfillment (JF) of the staff is cyclical because with this human needs want change. The Herzberg model is valuable in work satisfaction studies (Kim, 2004). It refers how the organization motivates employees and becomes productive. The conceptual framework (Figure 1) shows that core and external factors are the keys to achieve the best result in general occupation fulfillment. General Job satisfaction depends on the benefits of salaries, additional benefits, working conditions, work, and

achievements. If these factors are in a safe situation, “general occupation fulfillment of staff will remain positive and conducive to the organizational performance.

Research Objectives

- ❖ To identify the factors affecting Job fulfillment (JF) in Cement factories of Sindh.
- ❖ To examine intrinsic and extrinsic factors affecting Job fulfillment (JF) of employees in Cement factories of Sindh.
- ❖ To determine the most influential factors affecting Job fulfillment (JF) in Cement factories of Sindh.
- ❖ To analyze relationship between general occupations fulfillment (GOF) with extrinsic and intrinsic factors in Cement factories of Sindh.

Significance of Research

Cement industry is one of the top economic strategies among those few businesses that have found stability in the recent past in the subcontinent along with Pakistan. The real purpose behind the existence of this industry may be access to raw materials. Pakistan needs boundless shops around limestone what is more clay, which may support those businesses for an additional 50-60 long period of time. This year may be creating bonds towards the opportunity to form around Pakistan's best 300,000 tons per year. Eventually, in the 1954 Tom preparations was expanded 660000 tons per year against the interest of about 1 million tons for each year. In this range, through your hand taking activity further built two Zealpak bond processing plants (240,000 tons) and maple beet paper (100,000 tons) hosting a limit of 350,000 tons claimed, thus, expanding those preparations must be 1 million tons for each year. From that point forward, the development of existing plants, built a new plant as the population grows according to the demand. During that span, the staff was too much satisfied with the organization because it helps hand to increase production and hold the organization in a competitive market. In time need to know what factors affect the job fulfillment (JF) of employees in the organization because the human wants to change with time, Employees are the main assets of an organization. In this research we will be able to determine what kind of factors affect the job fulfillment (JF) of staff at flour mills in Sindh, Pakistan. The conceptual framework is shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Overall Satisfaction: Sector (1997) states that overall Job Satisfaction (OJS) from claiming workers ought to be characteristically investigated, previous evaluations and it inspected with various perspectives in distinctive classes. Such as, with certain characteristics of a job, particular case could b-e happy, percentages feel average; what's more some are despondent with others. The employment keeps vitality for distinctive levels which need aid those different features from claiming vocation which stays with weight period in light of particular occupation will be investigated through separate approaches due to dissecting the general occupation fulfillment (GOF). As stated, by Mullins, (2002) for couple of stages from claiming their work, the certain representatives could be a chance to fulfill it. As of the other periods they disappointed.

Salary Benefits: Various managers (what's more masters who partake) energizes those private sectors what's more legislature zones, they have confidence that those rising about salaries and fiscal reductions may be a supernatural strategy should expansion those in general occupation fulfillment (GOF). These thoughts would imparted by workers at the salaries increment will irrefutably expand Job fulfillment (JF) that will be sure impact looking into fill in inspiration. The expanded that specialist execution level (Dr. Marwan & t. Al-Zoubi) to pay to the representatives in a standout amongst influencing factors. What's more it doesn't just safeguards

for fundamental living, as well as progresses the personal satisfaction existence for representatives.

Working Conditions: As stated, by Robbins (2001), attempting surroundings demonstrates a paramount part starting with the occasion when the point when its effects on Job fulfillment (JF), Also Likewise specialists identify with physical working nature's domain will eventually diminish additional progressive level for job fulfillment (JF). Similarly, insufficiency for acceptable working states in number things might affect unwell on the employees' mental Furthermore physical prosperity (Baron Furthermore Greenberg, 2003). Clean Also alluring surroundings tend on make laborers content at completing their worth of effort abandons sure sway on job fulfillment (JF). There would thus a number things previously, attempting state impact looking into job fulfillment (JF) in the long run for example, viable communicating, viable attempting techniques, curtailed injuries, dissatisfaction What's more anxiety.

Fringe Benefits: Bernard (2007), states that border profits accentuate with respect to moving forward those personal satisfaction from claiming existence about representatives also advertising money related security What's more insurance level should specialists also their relatives to document maintaining, such similar to pay arrangements. The primary destination of associations through border reductions is should attract, hold furthermore inspired qualified What's more skillful representatives. Basically workers done Pakistan concentrate on border reductions in light their essential compensation doesn't enough help.

Work-itself: To representative fulfillment (RF) fill in itself assumes a critical part. The inventiveness for Worker enhances the benefits of the business limit to accomplish aggressive playing point. This detailed study does polishes around Innovativeness of the employees; et cetera that business must offer humble environment, challenging, Also differences from claiming meets expectations. Those workers will likewise empower should delight in their employments also need a feeling self-importance viewing it. Then afterward it constantly paid assortment for assignments on the same occupation representatives feel spurred What's more increased in value their autonomy, (Lam et al., 2001). Supervisors have will want employments will give acceptable chances for individual's accomplishment.

Achievements: Kaleemuallah (2010) depicts that representative fulfillment (RF) additionally increments at representative gets learning starting with finishing fill in. Achievements' targets basically would characterize similarly as the point when laborers attain normal focuses. When

bargain officer accomplishes commonplace focuses afterward it may be called destinations for achievements, here chief alternately co boss acclaims deals officer“ fill in will be known as appreciation about goal accomplishment. Human Resources (HR) chiefs must necessity on arrangement to convey beneficial chances to employees’ achievements which help done vocation arranging.

2. Research methodology

To the reason for information collection, quantitative strategy may be used. The quantitative study system is utilized within which an open finished far reaching questionnaire will be conveyed "around those workers of flour factories. The excellence from claiming this open wound questionnaire maybe it’s figured done three various dialects. One will be English language, second Urdu dialect and the third dialect is Sindhi. This methodology aided on gathers information starting with the individuals workers who are less educated, considerably uneducated representatives. Open finished questionnaire with multi dialects aided proficiently on gather information the information from flour factories workers for Sindh, Pakistan. As an exchange those Sindhi dialect arrangement reflected the honest to goodness longings of workers which are unfulfilled. We exactly define a generally speaking photograph that elements influence job fulfillment (JF) for representatives. Review questionnaire might have been loaded Eventually Tom's perusing representatives starting with June, 2014 will Feb, 2015. Previously, SPSS frequency, mean, correlation, pareto and cronbach alpha test are connected should inspect the inalienable Furthermore outward Components and figure out those The greater part persuasive variables general occupation fulfillment (GOF) ,and will examine the relationship the middle of innate Also outward Components with in general occupation fulfillment (GOF) of workers Previously, flour factories of Sindh. Those unwavering quality tests confirm those inquiries from claiming this research. Every last bit qualities are dependable and over 0.7 (Figure 2) which indicates adequate outcomes.

Figure 2: Alpha cronbach's after effect.

Sample design: This exploration information haphazardly gathered starting with 327 representatives who attempting on flour factories about Sindh with the open wound questionnaire is translated under English, Urdu What's more Sindhi dialects as will span the hole for this investigate.

Secondary data collection: Data is gathered starting with documents introduced basically and also tangibly. The auxiliary information for this examination will be assembled through books, Examine articles, what's more Websites.

Primary data collection: Gathered through the quantitative technique for which questionnaire need been used to accumulate information structure flour mills" workers from ten regions about Sindh. The quantitative technique may be aided to assemble greater part from claiming information for this examination. Supporting this, essential information expressed Eventually Tom's perusing Saunders Furthermore Thornhill (2007), "primary information will be gathered for the exploration will be with make undertaken".

Analysis and findings: Those information need been investigated through SPSS What's more MS- exceed expectations Factual devices which need aid utilized for examining data, mostly when generating tables, graphs Also figures. Factual Tests (Figure 3) would connected with assess those information over percentile, crosstabs, pareto analysis, What's more frequencies alongside Cronbach alpha unwavering quality test.

Figure 3: Overall job satisfaction

3. Results and Discussion

For getting the initially targeted results, 327 questionnaires were flowed to gain the legitimate reaction for 247 questionnaires respectively. The comes about of in general occupation fulfillment (GOF) need aid provided for bunch type in which it may be elucidated that minor about workers to flour plants are fulfilled by salary, investment over choice making, occasions polices, relationship with associates Furthermore supervisors, sustenance What's more refreshment office ,job secure, clean drinking water facility, settlement ,social securities, execution of work laws ,working uniform, Also particular occupation rotation, same time lion's share about workers need aid done cement factories (CF) would see fulfilled by mills' culture, boss support, occupation area ,and consciousness something like crisis. It will be finished up that workers would not fulfilled from A large portion about inquiries to in general occupation fulfillment (GOF) compelling reason change clinched alongside such factors.

To accomplishing the effects about objective no. 2 "To examine the intrinsic and extrinsic factors influencing job fulfillment (JF) to cement factories of Sindh", 317 questionnaires were flowed and gained correct reaction about 247 questionnaires. Those spellbinding facts test On SPSS need been connected should get percentile consequence from those recurrence table for each act.

As stated, salary benefits outcomes need aid provided for completely finished chart on group from. The inquiries would orchestrate together which approached starting with representatives would you fulfilled by the current salary, which 44. 5% representatives would determinedly disappoint with statement, 32. 2% workers about cement factories responded we are dis-satisfied

what's more 10% need aid Normal satisfied, 11. 7% workers responded we would fulfill. 4% responded we would determinedly fulfilled by the articulation. The point when those address approached from workers what amount of would you fulfilled by the development pay polices, they responded 32. 8% determinedly dissatisfied, for 38. 1% dissatisfied, 18% mills'' representatives responded they were Normal satisfied, 10. 4% found fulfilled What's more. 4% were determinedly fulfilled by those articulations. When inquiry approached type representatives are you euphoric for additional time arrangements about mills, they responded 0. 8% determinedly satisfied, with 3. 6%, 26% workers responded they were Normal satisfied, 60% were discovered disappointed Also 9. 7% determinedly disappointed with the proclamation. At inquiry approached type employees need aid you cheerful with overtime arrangements from claiming mills, they responded 0. 8% determinedly satisfied, for 3. 6%, 26% workers responded they were Normal satisfied, 60% were discovered disappointed and 9. 7% determinedly disappointed for those explanation. At address required starting with workers can Plant pay great as stated by those worth of effort load, representatives responded 1. 6% determinedly satisfied, for 22. 3% fulfilled, 13% responded they were Normal satisfied, 38. 5% were found disappointed Also 25. 1% determinedly disappointed with the proclamation.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Salary-benefits

Description	Number	Mean
Are you satisfied with the current salary	247	1.90
How much are you satisfied with the advance salary polices	247	2.07
Are you happy with overtime policies of mill	247	2.26
Does Mill pay well according to the work load	247	2.37

Above Table 1 indicates the effects about 247 employees'' reactions crazy about 317 for objective no. 2 with analyze the intrinsic What's more extrinsic factors influencing job fulfillment (JF) about workers clinched alongside cement factories of Sindh. Inquiries which would related for pay profits. On over table those mean quality from claiming pay reductions will be exhibited. It can would a chance to be elucidated those comes about through mean quality that representatives bring responded that cement factories'' owners would not appropriately working out for employees' salaries profits.

The highest mean value is 2.37 of query does factory wage well according to work lading in descriptive statistics of salary benefit category, and means value 2.26; are you happy with overtime policies of factory, while lowest mean value is 1.90 of question; are you satisfied with current salary? This value is less than normal. The result showed that 1.6% were strongly satisfied, with twenty-two .3% satisfied, 13% responded they were average satisfied, 38.5% were found dissatisfied and 25 .1% strongly dissatisfied with the statement. When question asked from employees do you easily manage the work load ? .8% employees were strongly satisfied, 11.7% satisfied, and 9.7% average satisfied, Little Joe 7.4% responded they were dissatisfied, and 30.4% were strongly dissatisfied. When question asked form employees are you happy with job autonomy? They responded 11% employees were satisfied, 14.2% found average satisfied, 45.7% were dissatisfied and 29.1% responded they were strongly dissatisfied.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Working Conditions

DESCRIPTION	NUMBER	MEAN
How much is working environment well	247	2.27
Do you easily manage the work load?	247	2.04
Are you happy with job autonomy?	247	2.07

Above tabular array deuce in Table 2 shows the outcome s of 247 employees“ reaction out of 317 for board of working conditions in which interrogative s are related with each other. The descriptive statistics test in SPSS is applied to see the result of mean value in which all mean value is less than 3 which have been responded by employees in which the highest value is 2.27 of question; how much is working environs well? Whereas lowest value is 2.04 of question; do you easily manage the work load? And it is very a hard question for an employee who is already involved in so many tasks in an industry. The job of a worker in the industry approaches many responsibilities which show his genuine interest.

Figure 4: Fringe benefits

The results are given in Figure 4 shows that the little phoebe with cluster form of fringe benefits“ category and head‘s’ are set together from which the first interrogative asked from employee how much are you satisfied from bonus policy of the mill?, they responded 7.3 % were satisfied, unity 0.1% uncovering average satisfied, Little 56 .3% responded they were dissatisfied, and 26.3% were strongly dissatisfied with the financial statement. When the question asked from employee how much are you satisfied from provident funds? They responded 5.7% employee were satisfied, 12 .1% found average satisfied, 47% responded they were dissatisfied and 35.2% were strongly dissatisfied. When question asked from employees how much are you satisfied from old age benefits? They responded 6.9% employees were satisfied, 15.4% found dissatisfying, 56.8 % responded they were dissatisfied and 27.9% were strongly dissatisfied. When question asked from employees are you satisfied from the facility of Transportation? They responded 62.4% employees were satisfied, 14.2% found satisfied, 16.6% were average satisfied ,responded 42.5% they were dissatisfied and 24.3% were strongly dissatisfied. When the question asked from employees how much are you satisfied from receiving gratuity fund? They responded 17% employees were satisfied, 12.1% found averagely satisfied, 36.4% responded they were dissatisfied and 38.8% were strongly dissatisfied with statement. When the question asked from employees are you happy due to promotion? They responded 13.4% employees were satisfied, 17.4% were found averagely satisfied, 32.4% were dissatisfied and 35.6% were strongly dissatisfied with statement. When the question asked from employees do you receive trainings? They responded.8% employees were strongly satisfied, 8.9% were satisfied, 13% were averagely satisfied, 42.1% were dissatisfied and 35.2% were strongly dissatisfied with statement.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of Fringe benefits

DESCRIPTION	No.	Mean
How much are you satisfied from bonus policies of the mill?	247	1.98
How much are you satisfied from provident funds	247	1.88
How much are you satisfied from old age benefits	247	2.01
Are you satisfied from the facility of Transportation	247	2.28
How much are you satisfied from receiving gratuity fund	247	2.13
Are you happy due to promotion	247	2.12
Do you receive trainings	247	1.98

Results of interference fringe benefits are described in Table 3 in which descriptive statistics test in SPSS is applied to stay the resultant role. In this table mean values of all interrogative s is less than 3 which have been responded by employee, in the table highest value is 2.28; are you satisfied from the facility of Transportation? While lowest value is 2.04 of question; how much are you satisfied from provident monetary fund? , through these results, it is clarified that minor employee who are working in factory are satisfied while majority of employees in factory are either strongly dissatisfied or dissatisfied which is determined that most of employees is demotivated towards the attitude of factory Before quitting the task from dedicated employees anatomy grinder and in return, factory should be improved the fringe benefits by which recruitment toll can reduce and growth satisfaction level of employees.

Figure 5: Work itself

The results of work itself category are given in clustered from Figure 5 in which inquiry 's' are arranged together from which the first question asked from employee are you got chance to do

different things from time to time? They responded.8 % employee were strongly satisfied, 26% were satisfied, 2.7% were averagely satisfied, 48.6% were dissatisfied and 32% were strongly dissatisfied with statement. When the question asked from employee is your job interesting? They responded. I 3% employee was strongly satisfied, 29.1% were satisfied, 13% responded they were dissatisfied, and 4.9% were strongly dissatisfied. When the question asked from employees work stress is easily manageable? They responded 8% employees were strongly satisfied, 18.2% were satisfied,23.5% responded they were average satisfied, 53.8% were dissatisfied, and 3.6% were strongly dissatisfied.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Work itself

DESCRIPTION	No.	MEAN
Is your job interesting?	247	2.50
Are you got chance to do different things from time to time?	247	2.67
Work Stress is easily manageable?	247	2.59

Above mean value in employment work is given in Table 4 in which 217 employee “ answers are included and all questions are arranged together and also related to piece of work itself category. It can be clarified that the mean value is less than 3 and going down from satisfaction level of employees.

Figure 6: Achievements

The resultant are given in Figure 6 seven in cluster form of Achievements class and questions are organized together from which the first question asked from employee are you learning from current job work? They responded triplet .deuce % employee were strongly dissatisfied, 48.6. %

were dissatisfied, 26.7% were averagely satisfied, 20.6% were satisfied and .8% were strongly
 When the question asked from employees how much are you satisfied from achievement? They
 answered that baker's dozen % employees were satisfied, 29.1% were averagely satisfied, 53%
 were dissatisfied and .4.9% were strongly dissatisfied. When the question asked from employees
 do you easily achieve the targets of job? They replied 13% employees were strongly satisfied,
 18.2% were dissatisfied, 23.5% were averagely satisfied, 53.8% responded employees were
 dissatisfied and 3.6% were strongly dissatisfied with statement.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Achievements

DESCRIPTION	No.	MEAN
How much are you satisfied from achievements	247	2.94
Are you learning from current job work	247	2.96
Do you easily achieve the targets of job	247	2.93

Above Table 5 of descriptive Ordered by Estimated Frequency) of noun statistic of accomplishment William Tell the result of 247 effective questionnaires" response which were circulated among ten territory of cement factory in Sindh. The above table in which questions are put shows that the all data relevant to accomplishment. Responses are taken form employee by Likert scale in which legal age of employees „response are either dissatisfied or needed improvement. Mean values of achievements „questions are less than trine and it is also less than satisfaction spirit level. It is indicating that it is not very satisfactory for employees. The cement industry is the building block of the nation's construction industry. Few construction projects can take place without utilizing cement somewhere in the design. Annual cement industry shipments are currently estimated at \$7.5 billion for 2012; up from \$6.6 billion in 2011. U.S. cement production is widely dispersed with the operation of 107 cement plants in 36 states. The top five companies collectively operate 49.6 percent of U.S. clinker capacity with the largest company representing 14.2 percent of all domestic clinker capacity. An estimated 76.7 percent of U.S. clinker capacity is owned by companies headquartered outside of the U.S.

Figure 7: Salary benefits

The third aim of this research discipline is to examine the most influential factor affecting Job fulfillments (JF) of employee in cement factories of Sindh in which we are applied the Pareto test to determine which ingredient are most influential divisor for Job fulfillment (JF) of employee . In above Figure 7, Pareto psychoanalysis test has been applied to make focus on main factors which will bring positive degree changes in other factors" event. are you satisfied with the stream earnings and does factory wages well according to the piece of work load are at highest precedence with mark ,while how much are you satisfied with the procession salary law and, I am happy with overtime policies of mills are at moderate priority. Current salary and workload are important and influenced factors, if flour mills focus on these factors then outcome of other factors will be resolved and it is possible when we will focus on responsible factor, over time polices, through it can get more positive results.

Figure 8: Working conditions

According to Pareto chart Figure 8 in which working environment is at highest antecedence and work load and job autonomy are at middle of the roader priority in line of score. Through Pareto analysis it is proved that working environment is one of influenced factors and needs to improve it, and then other factors automatically will be improved.

Figure 9: Fringe benefits

With help of Pareto chart Figure 9, we can know what influential factors effect on job fulfillment (JF) in context of fringe-benefit. Bonuses are at highest antecedence, breeding and furtherance, old age benefits are at moderated priority, and baksheesh fund and transportation at average priority. Bonuses, training, furtherance, and old age funds are influenced factors and provident fund is responsible factors through it can be focused on influenced factors then the best upshot can be achieved.

Figure 10: Work-itself

The results of the work itself are given in the Pareto Figure 10, and include the factors: your business is interesting the highest priorities and work can be easily controlled Stress is in a moderate priority in the context score. An interesting job is one of the factors influencing the achievements "category. If one of the factors improves in terms of work per se, then other factors will also be automatically improved to achieve the positive results in general occupation fulfillment (GOF) for staff at the cement factories in Sindh.

Figure 11: Achievements

According to the Pareto chart in Figure 11 the results of accomplishment are given, achievement broker include: how much are you satisfied from achievement is at highest antecedence and work Stress is easily manageable; and you learnedness from current job work and are at moderate priority with score. Achievements and learning's are influenced and important factors are found through Pareto chart. If flour mills bring positive changes in these factors, then positive changes will automatically be come in other factors.

Table 6. Correlation of Extrinsic Factors with the General Occupations Fulfillment (GOF)

1	General occupations fulfillment	Correlation	1
		Significance	
2	Salary benefits	Correlation	.479
		Significance	.002
3	Working conditions	Correlation	.174
		Significance	.483
4	Fringe benefits	Correlation	.528
		Significance	.028

To achieve the fourth substantive result, 317 forms were distributed to 10 regions Bond and got 247 questionnaires. Table 6 shows the output The relationship between external factors the general occupations fulfillment (GOF) that benefits from salaries The enormous benefits remain a positive and strong relationship with the general occupations fulfillment (GOF) The state of work remains positive but weakly correlated with the general occupations fulfillment (GOF). Can Conclusion that the presence of external factors is positive with the general occupations fulfillment (GOF) when these factors are improved, the general occupations fulfillment is increased (GOF).

Table 7. Correlation of Intrinsic Factors with General Occupations Fulfillment (GOF)

1	General occupations fulfillment	Correlation	
		Significance	1
2	Work-itself	Correlation	.461
		Significance	0 .14
3	Achievements	Correlation	.127
		Significance	.348

Table 7 shows the correlations between core factors and the general occupations fulfillment (GOF) in which the work itself maintains a strong and positive correlation with general occupations fulfillment (GOF) and achievement remains positive but weak correlation with the job fulfillment (JF), can be concluded that the correlation of the presence of intrinsic factors positive With general occupations fulfillment (GOF) because these factors are improved and general occupations fulfillment (OGF).

4. **Conclusion**

This research study logically demonstrates that there are many gaps in dealing with cement factories in the future for job fulfillment (JF) and overall job satisfaction (GOF) of employees. According to the results of this research, most employees are deprived of the form of reasonable salary benefits, Healthy working conditions, merit-based benefits, and learning from the same work Achievements. The staff will also feel comfortable and productive, at the cement factories, Employers are factors that affect employee job fulfillment (JF) of employees.

Recommendations

We are going to presents the incorporating recommendations for the outcomes factors which are affecting the job fulfillments (JF) and general occupation fulfillment of staff at the cement factories.

Salary benefits

- The current salary must be reasonable for staff where they can still be happy in the cement factories (Sindh).
- Cement factories (Sindh) must be paid to employees according to the size of work.
- Overtime and pre-pay policies should be improved.

Working conditions

- The working environment must be comfortable and that staff support in the Item for consumption Product work.
- The workload must be manageable so that most staffs are dissatisfied.
- The independence of jobs in the flour mill should be improved.

Margin benefits

- Additional benefits should be based on merit where staffs are understaffed, thus, saving the cost of employment.
- Training increases the skills and abilities of staff that require” (CFs).
- Promotion should be promoted on the merit of staff. The majority of staff not satisfied with savings funds, social security, reward funds, and old age.

Benefits to be improved

- Professional staffs uniforms must be available and work free of charge the fear.

Achievements

- Must focus on the work of the staff as they can learn from it.
- Cement factories (Sindh) should make the environment as good as the staff can achieve a day to goals of daily work.

Works by himself

- Cement factories (Sindh) should make the function comfortable as staff can work with their interests.
- Cement factories (Sindh) should give the staff a chance to do various jobs and trainings to get the experience.
- Work stress should be manageable.

Recommendations to the Government

- The government should establish a technical training institute in which it conducts technical courses for the employees.

- The Buildings structure development is developing in Pakistan generally, and then the government should focus on cement factories (Sindh) which must work like a professional business and concentrate on exporting its products. With these Opportunities, it will create and meet more incentives for existing employees.
- The government should start the cement factories project in one factory for each Sindh region, which will increase production through it, and the unemployment rate will be declined and "employee satisfaction will also increase despite the more margin benefits.
- Solve unscheduled load issue by shedding productions to increase a positive impact on employee job fulfillment.

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Dedication

Special thanks and dedication to my friend Mr. ZESHAN ABBAS

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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